

Rwala Bedouin

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Religious Group, Sunni

The Rwala Bedouin are nomadic pastoralists who move throughout southeastern Jordan and northern Saudi Arabia to sustain herds through the varying seasons. Traditionally, the Bedouin grazing territory extended north towards Damascus (as far as Homs), west bounded by Wādi Sirhān (an arid 200 mile-long depression along the border of Saudi Arabia and Jordan), east towards the Iraqi border (as far as Karbalā), and south towards Sakāka (bounded by the Nafūd desert). More recently, “their relationship to land has been altered by the creation of nation-states in the 20th century and the establishment of national boundaries across their customary migration routes” (Young, 2009). This entry focuses on the Rwala Bedouin living in northern Saudi Arabia around the time of 1913. The Rwala Bedouin are Sunni Muslims, and believe in an omnipresent high god: In addition to Allāh are the inhabitants of the celestial world (malājika) and the inhabitants of the spiritual earthly world (ʿjinn), which were both created by Allāh. No full-time religious specialists are present. Individuals who are more knowledgeable or literate in Arabic might lead prayers, but each individual is ultimately responsible for their own religious practice. For the Rwala Bedouin, religion is bound up with all aspects of life. Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society at large.

Date Range: 1887 CE - 1915 CE

Region: Bedouin grazing territory, Saudi Arabia

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Saudi Arabia

Bedouin grazing territory, Saudi Arabia ca.1913

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 2: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=md04-000>

– Source 1 Description: Young, William. 2009. "Culture Summary: Rwala Bedouin." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=md04-002>

– Source 2 Description: Musil, Alois. 1928. "Manners And Customs Of The Rwala Bedouins." Oriental Explorations And Studies. New York: The American Geographical Society.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=md04-001>

– Source 3 Description: Raswan, Carl Reinhard. 1947. "Black Tents Of Arabia." New York: Creative Age Press.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala are Sunni Muslims. They observe the five pillars of Islam (declaration of faith, daily worship, almsgiving, fasting Ramadān, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009). As Muslims, the Rwala Bedouins follow the teachings of the Koran. However, the Koran is not extensively described in ethnographic accounts.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6:Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 375000

Notes: "Lancaster estimated that in 1978 there were between 250,000 and 500,000 Rwala, of whom most were living inside Saudi Arabia. There is no census of their highly mobile population" (Young, 2009).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1977 CE - 1978 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6:Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Rwala Bedouin would actively recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "The Bedouin does not think deeply on religious matters and follows no rules in his religious observances. Nevertheless, he guides himself in all his social and private undertakings by certain fixed customs, observes the various natural phenomena, and pays heed to internal impulses and dreams which he holds to be signs or warnings sent to him by spiritual beings who wish him either good or ill" (Musil, 1928:389).

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: "Like most other Sunnis, the Rwala do not have a clergy or full-time religious specialists" (Young, 2009).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6:Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "Like most other Sunnis, the Rwala do not have a clergy or full-time religious specialists. Those who are literate in Arabic sometimes lead group prayers. Each individual is responsible for his own religious practice (prayer, fasting Ramadān, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009). "Among the Bedouins there are persons, both male and female, who know and see hidden things and are able to heal the sick. The Rwala call them collectively ahl as-sirr or as-serrijje, and individually rā' as-sirr, a lord (or owner) of secrets, seer, whereas they are known among themselves as as-hāb al-islām, owners of islām, possessing the protection of God. They maintain that they inherit their supernatural qualities, their islām, from their forefathers and that, therefore, the ability to heal the sick, discover what is hidden, foretell the future, etc., is confined to certain families. This the Rwala refuse to believe and often deride the seers openly. If, however, both the seer's father and grandfather were also known as seers or sorcerers, then the Bedouins may admit the claim to be justified; but they scoff the more at the men and women who, having joined the seer, begin after some time to claim that they too have been endowed by Allāh with the gifts of islām" (Musil, 1928:400). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Membership/Group Interactions

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Rwala Bedouin would actively recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 375000

Notes: "Lancaster estimated that in 1978 there were between 250,000 and 500,000 Rwala, of whom most were living inside Saudi Arabia. There is no census of their highly mobile population" (Young, 2009).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1977 CE - 1978 CE

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "Like most other Sunnis, the Rwala do not have a clergy or full-time religious specialists. Those who are literate in Arabic sometimes lead group prayers. Each individual is responsible for his own religious practice (prayer, fasting Ramadān, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009). "Among the Bedouins there are persons, both male and female, who know and see hidden things and are able to heal the sick. The Rwala call them collectively ahl as-sirr or as-serrijje, and individually râ' as-sirr, a lord (or owner) of secrets, seer, whereas they are known among themselves as as-hâb al-islâm, owners of islâm, possessing the protection of God. They maintain that they inherit their supernatural qualities, their islâm, from their forefathers and that, therefore, the ability to heal the sick, discover what is hidden, foretell the future, etc., is confined to certain families. This the Rwala refuse to believe and often deride the seers openly. If, however, both the seer's father and grandfather were also known as seers or sorcerers, then the Bedouins may admit the claim to be justified; but they scoff the more at the men

and women who, having joined the seer, begin after some time to claim that they too have been endowed by Allâh with the gifts of islâm" (Musil, 1928:400). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala are Sunni Muslims. They observe the five pillars of Islam (declaration of faith, daily worship, almsgiving, fasting Ramadân, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009). As Muslims, the Rwala Bedouins follow the teachings of the Koran. However, the Koran is not extensively described in ethnographic accounts.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6:Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 6:Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings".

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "...every living man has a soul, nesem. If there were no soul, he would not live. The soul cannot be seen but can be heard, being identical with the breath, ar-rûh h'w an-nesem. The soul of the first man was breathed by Allâh into the nostrils, hence the human soul originates from Allâh's breath...The nesem dwells in the man's inside, bečabdeh wa-bsadreh. On the man's death the soul leaves his body through the nostrils, returns to Allâh..." (Musil, 1928:673). [Note: some accents omitted from native words]

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "When a Rwejlî falls asleep, his soul, nesem or rûh, leaves his body through the nostrils, visits his relatives and the old camping grounds, goes out on raids, plays all sorts of incredible pranks, agâjeb, eats and drinks, and the man will not awaken until his soul returns through the nostrils once more" (Musil, 1928:398). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of the deceased, sajâteh radijje. Allâh punishes sins: az-zena, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, bowk, of persons to whom the females belong; al-howne, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; dabh az-zelema, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; az-zelîme, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

— Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

Are supernatural beings present:

— Yes

Notes: "The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malājika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgānn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allāh" (Musil, 1928:411).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

— Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, High Gods [note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34], indicates that a high god is present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

— I don't know

Notes: "Allāh dwells in both paradise and hell. He is omnipresent, hears and sees everything, but is himself invisible" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

— Yes

Notes: "The Rwala know that Heaven is the abode of God who looks after them and supplies them with food" (Musil, 1928:86). "Allāh dwells in both paradise [below the ground] and hell [above the Earth]" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

— Yes

Notes: "Allāh dwells in both paradise [below the ground] and hell [above the Earth]" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

— No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Rwala Bedouin.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

— No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Rwala Bedouin.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Allâh dwells in both paradise and hell. He is omnipresent, hears and sees everything, but is himself invisible" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:675)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:675)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:675)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "All Rwala believe that they can win Allâh's favor by a vow. Not that Allâh would desire or need the promised object, but it rejoices him to see that the Bedouins remember in time that without his help they cannot attain what they desire, and also that they show willingness to give up something of value in order to assure themselves of his help. Such vows are made by all, men as well as women, old as well as young, in regard to their various needs and in all sorts of ways" (Musil, 1928:420-421).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Notes: "With Allâh's permission even the dead may leave either paradise or hell and visit their kin, to whom they appear in dreams" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malâjika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgânn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allâh...To the earthly spirits, ʿginn, harâfil, or ʿgenûn, heaven is not accessible. They are of both sexes and have big eyes extending to the corners of their mouths. The food they prefer is raw meat, nej, and fresh blood is their favorite drink" (Musil, 1928:411).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Some of the earthly spirits are given to harming men and take on various shapes for that purpose. They have various names. Of these most dreaded by the Bedouins is a female spirit called sarat aš-šîbe. In appearance she is a tall thin woman wearing a dress made of leather. This spirit wanders about the desert from camp to camp, looking for children. If she hears a child crying, she crawls near, gropes about for it with her hands till she finds it, then catches it, and runs with it to her own kin" (Musil, 1928:416). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: "Woe to the Bedouin who falls asleep in a region inhabited by the spirits! For if a ʿgânnijje observes him, she crawls into his body either through his nostrils, forefinger, or big toe, and, as soon as she gets hold of him, she makes him jump up and run into the desert, whence he can be brought back to his tent only by force. A man so possessed is known as mahšûš or muharfal. To cure him, a seer, râ as-sirr, is called in..." (Musil, 1928:412). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "To the earthly spirits, ʿginn, harâfil, or ʿgenûn, heaven is not accessible. They are of both sexes and have big eyes extending to the corners of their mouths. The food they

prefer is raw meat, nej, and fresh blood is their favorite drink. The raw meat they get from fallen animals, the blood is left for them by the Bedouins every time an animal is killed" (Musil, 1928:411).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malâjjika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgânn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allâh" (Musil, 1928:411).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "As long as there is a nesem [soul] in the man, he lives, nesemeh beh hajj, but when it leaves his body, he dies. The nesem departs through his nostrils, jetla min al-manhar. After his death the deceased is suspended in the air above his grave, head upwards. His nesem floats over his head. Thus it remains till the hbâta sacrifice has been brought, after which the body takes its place in the grave and the nesem departs, no one knows where" (Musil, 1928:673-674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words]

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Hell is situated either on the sun or in some other place above the earth. There the sun scorches by day and night, rains are very rare, the breeding of camels meets with no success, the soil has to be irrigated artificially – and the Bedouins there must work long and hard. They serve the fellâhîn, have to obey the government, are conscripted, perform military duty, and Allâh himself knows all their torments. Some call hell dalfât and think that in that place neither the moon nor the stars ever shine" (Musil, 1928:675). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Paradise is somewhere below ground. There it rains regularly, there is always rabî, abundance, good pasture, hejr, and there also the moon shines all the time. In paradise all the Rwala live together, are young, and never grow older. They can marry there and have grown children at once. Every one has a big tent, big herds, and many children. They raid hostile tribes which have been condemned to hell, where all enemies of the

Rwala are sent" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of the deceased, sajâteh radijje. Allâh punishes sins: az-zena, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, bowk, of persons to whom the females belong; al-howne, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; dabh az-zelema, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; az-zelîme, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: (Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: (Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of the deceased, sajâteh radijje. Allâh punishes sins: az-zena, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, bowk, of persons to whom the females belong; al-howne, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; dabh az-zelema, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; az-zelîme, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "In this world he [Allah] punishes by disease, by sending robbers against the sinner's estate; by taking away his sons, or by having him murdered" (Musil, 1928:674).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674)

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "When a child is born, it receives the nesem from its mother, to whom Allâh adds from his own breath every time she conceives. The nesem dwells in the man's inside, bečabdeh wa-b□adreh On the man's death the soul leaves his body through the nostrils, returns to Allâh, and waits till another mother conceives a man, ins, when Allâh will add the waiting soul to that of the mother" (Musil, 1928:673). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating a belief in reincarnation in animal/plant form.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating a belief in reincarnation in the form of an inanimate object.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– I don't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence to make a clear conclusion.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "They do not close the eyes of the dead, nor stop his nostrils, dead bodies being carefully avoided by the Rwaia. If they camp near a settlement, or some fellahin happen to be with them at the time, they hire them to bury the dead. Rubbing the body over with a wet cloth, they wrap it in its shirt, or when that is torn they lay it on a piece of white linen, cover it with the same material, then sew both pieces in three places, load the body thus enshrouded on a mule and carry it to the grave. This must be deeper for a woman than for a man. Its depth for a woman must be such that even the breast could not be seen if the body were placed upright; for the man its depth is only to his knees when in a standing posture. A stone is put under the head and the body is laid invariably with its right side downwards and facing south. Covering it then with a few stones they shovel in the excavated earth. For a man two stones, nasajeb, are raised above the grave, one for a woman... In the inner desert a grave about twenty-five centimeters deep is dug anywhere, the body wrapped in its cloak, aba, laid into it on its right side and facing south; then all is covered with stones or earth" (Musil, 1928:670-671). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "This [the grave] must be deeper for a woman than for a man. Its depth for a woman must be such that even the breast could not be seen if the body were placed upright; for the man its depth is only to his knees when in a standing posture. A stone is put under the head and the body is laid invariably with its right side downwards and facing south. Covering it then with a few stones they shovel in the excavated earth. For a man two stones, nasajeb, are raised above the grave, one for a woman... In the inner desert a grave about twenty-five centimeters deep is dug anywhere, the body wrapped in its cloak, aba, laid into it on its right side and facing south; then all is covered with stones or earth" (Musil, 1928:670-671). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: on side

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of secondary burials.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of re-treatment of corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic details concerning burials.

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "...every living man has a soul, nesem. If there were no soul, he would not live. The soul cannot be seen but can be heard, being identical with the breath, ar-rûh h'w an-nesem. The soul of the first man was breathed by Allâh into the nostrils, hence the human soul originates from Allâh's breath...The nesem dwells in the man's inside, bečabdeh wa-bsadreh. On the man's death the soul leaves his body through the nostrils, returns to Allâh..." (Musil, 1928:673). [Note: some accents omitted from native words]

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "When a Rwejlî falls asleep, his soul, nesem or rûh, leaves his body through the nostrils, visits his relatives and the old camping grounds, goes out on raids, plays all sorts of incredible pranks, agâjeb, eats and drinks, and the man will not awaken until his soul returns through the nostrils once more" (Musil, 1928:398). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "As long as there is a nesem [soul] in the man, he lives, nesemeh beh hajj, but when it leaves his body, he dies. The nesem departs through his nostrils, jetla min al-manhar. After his death the deceased is suspended in the air above his grave, head upwards. His nesem floats over his head. Thus it remains till the hbâta sacrifice has been brought, after which the body takes its place in the grave and the nesem departs, no one knows where" (Musil, 1928:673-674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words]

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Hell is situated either on the sun or in some other place above the earth. There the sun scorches by day and night, rains are very rare, the breeding of camels meets with no success, the soil has to be irrigated artificially – and the Bedouins there must work long and hard. They serve the fellâhîn, have to obey the government, are conscripted, perform military duty, and Allâh himself knows all their torments. Some call hell dalfât and think that in that place neither the moon nor the stars ever shine" (Musil, 1928:675). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Paradise is somewhere below ground. There it rains regularly, there is always rabî, abundance, good pasture, hejr, and there also the moon shines all the time. In paradise all the Rwala live together, are young, and never grow older. They can marry there and have grown children at once. Every one has a big tent, big herds, and many children. They raid hostile tribes which have been condemned to hell, where all enemies of the Rwala are sent" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "When a child is born, it receives the nesem from its mother, to whom Allâh adds from his own breath every time she conceives. The nesem dwells in the man's inside, bečabdeh wa-b□adreh On the man's death the soul leaves his body through the nostrils, returns to Allâh, and waits till another mother conceives a man, ins, when Allâh will add the waiting soul to that of the mother" (Musil, 1928:673). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating a belief in reincarnation in animal/plant form.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating a belief in reincarnation in the form of an inanimate object.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– I don't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "They do not close the eyes of the dead, nor stop his nostrils, dead bodies being carefully avoided by the Rwala. If they camp near a settlement, or some fellahin happen to be with them at the time, they hire them to bury the dead. Rubbing the body over with a wet cloth, they wrap it in its shirt, or when that is torn they lay it on a piece of white linen, cover it with the same material, then sew both pieces in three places, load the body thus enshrouded on a mule and carry it to the grave. This must be deeper for a woman than for a man. Its depth for a woman must be such that even the breast could not be seen if the body were placed upright; for the man its depth is only to his knees when in a standing posture. A stone is put under the head and the body is laid invariably with its right side downwards and facing south. Covering it then with a few stones they shovel in the excavated earth. For a man two stones, nasajeb, are raised above the grave, one for a woman... In the inner desert a grave about twenty-five centimeters deep is dug anywhere, the body wrapped in its cloak, aba, laid into it on its right side and facing south; then all is covered with stones or earth" (Musil, 1928:670-671). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "This [the grave] must be deeper for a woman than for a man. Its depth for a woman must be such that even the breast could not be seen if the body were placed upright; for the man its depth is only to his knees when in a standing posture. A stone is put under the head and the body is laid invariably with its right side downwards and facing south. Covering it then with a few stones they shovel in the excavated earth. For a man two stones, nasajeb, are raised above the grave, one for a woman... In the inner desert a grave about twenty-five centimeters deep is dug anywhere, the body wrapped in its cloak, aba, laid into it on its right side and facing south; then all is covered with stones or earth" (Musil, 1928:670-671). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: on side

Notes: Musil, 1928:670-671

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of secondary burials.

Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of re-treatment of corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic details concerning burials.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malājika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgānn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allāh" (Musil, 1928:411).

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, High Gods [note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34], indicates that a high god is present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

Notes: "Allāh dwells in both paradise and hell. He is omnipresent, hears and sees everything, but is himself invisible" (Musil, 1928:675).

The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala know that Heaven is the abode of God who looks after them and supplies them with food" (Musil, 1928:86). "Allâh dwells in both paradise [below the ground] and hell [above the Earth]" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Notes: "Allâh dwells in both paradise [below the ground] and hell [above the Earth]" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Rwala Bedouin.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Rwala Bedouin.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Allâh dwells in both paradise and hell. He is omnipresent, hears and sees everything, but is himself invisible" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Musil, 1928:675)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:675)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: "All Rwala believe that they can win Allâh's favor by a vow. Not that Allâh would desire or need the promised object, but it rejoices him to see that the Bedouins remember in time that without his help they cannot attain what they desire, and also that they show willingness to give up something of value in order to assure themselves of his help. Such vows are made by all, men as well as women, old as well as young, in regard to their various needs and in all sorts of ways" (Musil, 1928:420-421).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– I don't know

Notes: "With Allâh's permission even the dead may leave either paradise or hell and visit their kin, to whom they appear in dreams" (Musil, 1928:675).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malâjika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgânn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allâh...To the earthly spirits, ʿginn, harâfil, or ʿgenûn, heaven is not accessible. They are of both sexes and have big eyes extending to the corners of their mouths. The food they prefer is raw meat, nej, and fresh blood is their favorite drink" (Musil, 1928:411).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

Notes: "Some of the earthly spirits are given to harming men and take on various shapes for that purpose. They have various names. Of these most dreaded by the Bedouins is a female spirit called sarat aš-šîbe. In appearance she is a tall thin woman wearing a dress made of leather. This spirit wanders about the desert from camp to camp, looking for children. If she hears a child crying, she crawls near, gropes about for it with her hands till she finds it, then catches it, and runs with it to her own kin" (Musil, 1928:416). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: "Woe to the Bedouin who falls asleep in a region inhabited by the spirits! For if a ʿgânnijje observes him, she crawls into his body either through his nostrils, forefinger, or big toe, and, as soon as she gets hold of him, she makes him jump up and run into the desert, whence he can be brought back to his tent only by force. A man so possessed is known as mahšûš or muharfal. To cure him, a seer, râ as-sirr, is called in..." (Musil, 1928:412). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "To the earthly spirits, ʿginn, harâfil, or ʿgenûn, heaven is not accessible. They are of both sexes and have big eyes extending to the corners of their mouths. The food they prefer is raw meat, nej, and fresh blood is their favorite drink. The raw meat they get from fallen animals, the blood is left for them by the Bedouins every time an animal is killed" (Musil, 1928:411).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala believe that besides this visible world there is also an invisible, or spiritual, world. The spiritual world is again divided into a celestial and an earthly world. The inhabitants of the celestial world are called malak (pl., malâjika), those of the spiritual earthly world ʿgânn (pl., ʿginn). Both the celestial and earthly spirits were created by Allâh" (Musil, 1928:411).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of the deceased, sajâteh radijje. Allâh punishes sins: az-zena, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, bowk, of persons to whom the

females belong; al-howne, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; dabh az-zelema, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; az-zelîme, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the

agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Allah is the only supernatural being described (in the ethnographic materials) as the agent of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of the deceased, sajâteh radijje. Allâh punishes sins: az-zena, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, bowk, of persons to whom the females belong; al-howne, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; dabh az-zelema, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; az-zelîme, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: (Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: (Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "After the zahijje sacrifice Allâh weighs both the good deeds, hasanateh, and the sins of

the deceased, *sajâteh radijje*. Allâh punishes sins: *az-zena*, which means sexual intercourse with a girl betrothed to another or with another's wife, for that is a betrayal, *bowk*, of persons to whom the females belong; *al-howne*, the robbery of a guest or companion who has trusted one while on the road; *dabh az-zelema*, killing of a man not subject to the blood feud or of an enemy who did not attack one; *az-zelîme*, false testimony under oath before the court. These four sins alone are punished by Allâh both in this world and hereafter" (Musil, 1928:674). [Note: Some accents omitted from native words].

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "In this world he [Allah] punishes by disease, by sending robbers against the sinner's estate; by taking away his sons, or by having him murdered" (Musil, 1928:674).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Musil, 1928:674)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence to make a clear conclusion.

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Notes: Fasting during *Ramadân* is practiced, but it is unclear if fasting is required. "Each individual is responsible for his own religious practice (prayer, fasting *Ramadân*, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala celebrate the two central Islamic holidays: the holiday of sacrifice (ʿīd al-adḥa) and the holiday of breaking fast (ʿīd al-fitr) which ends the month of fasting during Ramadan. Other than these religious holidays, the main ceremonies are: boys' circumcisions, weddings, and funerals. Of these, circumcisions were traditionally the most public and most elaborate" (Young, 2009).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin "...consider circumcision for boys to be an Islamic obligation. But they don't have religious specialists associated with this rite of passage" (Young, 2009).

Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin "...consider circumcision for boys to be an Islamic obligation. But they don't have religious specialists associated with this rite of passage" (Young, 2009).

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Notes: Fasting during Ramadān is practiced, but it is unclear if fasting is required. "Each individual is responsible for his own religious practice (prayer, fasting Ramadān, and pilgrimage)" (Young, 2009).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The Rwala celebrate the two central Islamic holidays: the holiday of sacrifice (ʿīd al-adḥā) and the holiday of breaking fast (ʿīd al-fitr) which ends the month of fasting during Ramadan. Other than these religious holidays, the main ceremonies are: boys' circumcisions, weddings, and funerals. Of these, circumcisions were traditionally the most public and most elaborate" (Young, 2009).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

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Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin "...consider circumcision for boys to be an Islamic obligation. But they don't have religious specialists associated with this rite of passage" (Young, 2009).

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community [note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas Column 32] indicates that the Rawala Bedouin have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of petty chiefdoms (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 10: Police), "police functions are not specialized or institutionalize at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery".

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin rely predominantly on pastoralism for subsistence. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin rely predominantly on pastoralism for subsistence. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

- Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 9: Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is exercised by independent hereditary functionaries". "More serious differences are settled among the Rwala by the hereditary native judge, ârefa (pl., awâref). Judicial dignity is hereditary in certain kins and passes as a rule from father to son" (Musil, 1948:426-427). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

- No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A chiefdom

Notes: SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community [note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas Column 32] indicates that the Rawala Bedouin have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of petty chiefdoms (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (Food Storage) indicates that no food storage is present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 10: Police), "police functions are not specialized or institutionalize at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery".

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 9: Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is exercised by independent hereditary functionaries". "More serious differences are settled among the Rwala by the hereditary native judge, ârefa (pl., awâref). Judicial dignity is hereditary in certain kins and passes as a rule from father to son" (Musil, 1948:426-427). [Note: some accents omitted from native words].

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin rely predominantly on pastoralism for subsistence. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism

Notes: The Rwala Bedouin rely predominantly on pastoralism for subsistence. Hunting and gathering supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.